

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to determine the organizational dynamics and participative work culture in appraising school environment effectiveness in the targeted Schools in Tiaong 1 District. The independent variable in the study based on organizational dynamics and participative work culture. The dependent variable was geared towards the school environment effectiveness in terms of teachers' performance, learning outcome and school impact.

This study used a descriptive and correlational type of research to determine the organizational dynamics and participative work culture in appraising school environment, effectiveness it involved 180 teachers in the District of Tiaong I, and the data gathered were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment-Correlation. Since there is a significant relationship between the experienced organizational dynamics and school environment effectiveness. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated in study is not supported. Participative work culture is significantly related to school environment effectiveness in terms of teachers' performance, learning outcome and school impact. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated in study is not supported.

KEYWORDS: Organizational dynamics; Participative, Work culture; School environment effectiveness

1. INTRODUCTION

The term "school organization" describes how educational institutions set up their employees, time, and physical space to best support student learning. The organizational structure of the school takes these difficulties into account. Organization in schools is really important. The effectiveness of the institution, ensuring the school's benefits through practical measures, clarifying the school's functions, coordinating the educational programs, sound educational planning, good direction, and efficient and methodical execution are all included. It offers intimate cooperation, a sense of sharing duties, a focused goal, and a flexible strategy. Any organization plays a vital role in the life of human being. School organization plays different functions like; brings efficiency, guide students to receive right direction from the right teachers, enables the students to get profit from their learning, bring coordination of the student-teacher-parents-society. It provides well defined policies and programs, favorable teaching learning situation, growth and development of human beings, make use of appropriate materials, effective development of human qualities, execution of the programs, arrangement of the activities, efforts for attainment of the objectives (Joseph, 2017).

Organizations face challenges while they live in a dynamic and competitive environment. The effectiveness of organization constitutes its ability to perform a function with optimal levels of input and output. Improving organizational effectiveness is a sober concern for any organization as a matter of existence. This has to be achieved through implementation of important organizational effectiveness factors. Enhancing organizational effectiveness is the key for success in any work and consequently leaders are expected to increase the efficiency of their work environment (Mohan, 2021).

When instructors are struggling to perform their duties, a well-run educational institution like the school can be of tremendous assistance, especially in urgent situations. For instance, when more work must be completed in a shorter length of time, performance falls. It is essential that the school, the administration, and the teaching and non-teaching personnel all function in a supportive, motivating environment under this circumstance. The drive to behave in conformity with expectations inspires a person. The extent and duration of a person's work commitment serve as proxies for their level of motivation. While a person who is highly motivated achieves and performs well, a person who is unmotivated or poorly motivated has little drive to do things effectively. That force can be amplified by something external to the individual, internal to them, or by the activity itself (Bergström E. et al., 2016).

An organization is a building or a group of individuals working together to accomplish a common objective. To put it another way, an organization is a social relationship that a group of individuals form in order to accomplish a specific aim or goal. The educational system is an administrative organization that represents a variety of forces and elements from a sociological standpoint. As an educational institution, the school helps the students acquire the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to meet the objectives

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

and tenets of the educational system. The school can be managed within the context of relationships and its position within society as well as as a social organization on its own. The school and the society are the structures within the complicated and interdependent relation (Procedia 2015).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Organizational Dynamics

The study of Beauchamp (2021) looked into how independent school administrators saw their leadership growth. The administrators believe that a structured mentor program could help them enhance their leadership skills, especially if it is tailored to the organization's needs.

School organizations are composed of individuals who have different socioeconomic status, style of living, rules and values. Today, successful leaders have to care about school culture, pay attention to the pressures of change and holistically evaluate their organizations' environment. Specifically, the wide-angle view related to the school culture offers leaders a broader framework for a deeper understanding of school climate and complex relationships within the school organization. Despite lacks a clear definition in the field of education, school culture is defined as a style of living organizations which differentiate between the societies and between the organizations and “deep patterns of values, beliefs, and traditions that have been formed throughout of the school's history” (Atasoy 2020).

2.2 Participative Work Culture

Participative work cultures empower individuals and give them a sense of ownership in their work and the school environment. When teachers and other staff members feel valued and involved in decision-making, they become more engaged and committed to their roles (Barkhuizen et al., 2017). This increased ownership and engagement translate into improved teaching practices, better student support, and a positive learning atmosphere, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of the school environment. Moreover, Enhanced Problem-solving and Innovation in a participative work culture encourages diverse perspectives and ideas, promoting problem-solving and innovation within the school environment. When individuals are given the opportunity to contribute their insights and experiences, they bring fresh ideas to address challenges and find creative solutions (Davis et al., 2019). This culture of problem-solving and innovation leads to continuous improvement in teaching methodologies, curriculum development, and student support systems, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of the school environment. Furthermore, strengthened Trust and Morale in a participative work culture nurtures trust and mutual respect among stakeholders. When teachers and administrators feel their opinions are valued and that they have a voice in decision-making processes, it builds trust and strengthens relationships within the school community (Hassan et al., 2018). This trust and positive morale contribute to a supportive and cohesive environment, fostering teamwork, collaboration, and ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of the school environment.

Workplace culture is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. Filipinos take pride in their profession and emphasize developing relationships with others to better provide for their families and the success of their institutions. If learning is to occur, new ideas are required, and these ideas are the catalyst for organizational change (Howard-Grenville et al., 2014).

2.3 School Effective Environment

Teachers are key actors who shape the learning environment and whose main tasks include motivating students to learn. Teachers can differ in the way in which they try to motivate students to learn and their motivational strategies. One of the most important tasks of teacher is to create a learning environment that enhances and sustains students' motivation and engages students in learning. Teachers usually hold very stable long-term beliefs about the nature of student motivation and the particular motivational strategies that are effective in motivating their students. Motivated teachers are “enthusiastic, resourceful, creative and strict”. Motivated learners, on the other hand, are “more enthusiastic, goal-oriented, committed, persistent, and confident in their learning”. They work hard to achieve their goal and never give up (Stroet, 2013).

3 METHODOLOGY

The researcher used the descriptive correlational of research in conducting the study. Specifically, it utilized correlational. McCombes, (2019) claims that descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon. It can answer what, when, where, when, and how questions, but not why questions. To determine cause and effect, experimental research is required.

Correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them. A correlation reflects the strength or direction of the relationship between two (or more) variables. The direction of a correlation can be either positive or negative (Bhandari, 2021).

The respondents of the study were the public elementary teachers of Tiaong I District, Division of Quezon. Specifically, it included 180 teachers from different schools of Tiaong District I, Division of Quezon.

The research instrument used in the conduct of the study was survey questionnaire. The survey questionnaire was designed and developed by the researcher with the guidance of individuals who are experts in questionnaire development. Validation of the

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

questionnaire was done content validation, that is, by means of experts' as to the degree to which the instrument logically appears to measure the intended variable and to validate consistency and reliability of the statements in the questionnaire.

A questionnaire is the term used to describe the set of questions you're asking an individual. A survey is the process of collecting, analyzing and interpreting data from many individuals. It aims to determine insights about a group of people. A survey goes much deeper than a questionnaire and often involves more than one form of data collection. It is validated by a group of experts who have characteristics similar to the subjects of the study but who are not directly involved in the conduct of research.

For the refinement of the research instrument, it was submitted to the research adviser for evaluation of the content and sequential organization of the instrument. Through them, the content of the questionnaire was modified and revised accordingly. Their comments and suggestions are highly considered for the final structuring of the questionnaire then, distributing the questionnaires to the actual respondent follows immediately after the approval of the panel of examiners.

Purposely for the use in the study organizational dynamics and participative work culture questionnaire in appraising school environment effectiveness was composed of 90 items.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

Name of School	No. of Teaching Personnel	Actual Respondents
Aquino Elementary School	7	5
Ayusan Elementary School	16	13
Behia Elementary School	11	8
Bukal Elementary School	17	12
Bula Elementary School	11	9
Bulakin Elementary School	15	11
Claro M. Recto Memorial Central School	56	48
Doña Concepcion H. Umali Elementary School	20	14
Lalig Elementary School	8	6
San Agustin Elementary School	9	7
San Francisco Elementary School	8	5
San Jose Elementary School	11	9
San Pedro Elementary School	13	10
Tamisian Elementary School	8	7
Tiaong East Elementary School	23	16
Total	233	180

The respondents of the study were the public elementary teachers of Tiaong I District, Division of Quezon. Specifically, it included 180 teachers from different schools of Tiaong District I, Division of Quezon.

Table 2. Organizational Dynamics Experienced in Exploitative Authoritative Strategy

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school...			
1. roles are directly imposed on teachers..		4.19 0.78	ME
2. teamwork and communication are minimal.		3.61 1.23	ME
3. decisions of school heads are imposed and responsibility is at the upper levels of the organizational hierarchy		4.06 0.95	ME
4. employees may engage in a counter-productive behavior.		3.95 0.94	ME
5. there is little to no trust in school personnel		3.18 1.44	E
Overall	3.80	1.07	ME

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Experienced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Experienced, 2.50-3.49 Experienced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Experienced, 1.00-1.49 Not Experienced

Table 2 reveals that four statement obtained the highest mean interpreted as "mostly experienced" and interpreted as "experienced" which refers to statement 5. In total, the respondents' perceived organizational dynamics experienced in terms of Exploitative Authoritative is "mostly experienced". School roles are directly imposed on teachers from the school heads under the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers, teacher has a regular full-time teaching load and is mandated to devote a maximum of six hours of actual classroom instruction a day.

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

Table 3. Organizational Dynamics Experienced in terms of Benevolent Authoritative Strategy

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school...			
1. decision-making is extends to middle- managerial levels.	4.02	0.70	ME
2. limited employee consultation on decisions exist.	3.51	1.17	ME
3. team members commonly compete for rewards.	3.34	1.31	E
4. rewards for performance exists, but also offers a threat for punishment.	3.24	1.37	E
5. there is more trust toward employees is evident.	3.97	0.89	ME
Overall	3.62	1.09	ME

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Experienced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Experienced, 2.50-3.49 Experienced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Experienced, 1.00-1.49 Not Experienced

Table 3 reveals that there are three statement which obtained the highest mean interpreted as “mostly experienced” and interpreted as “experienced” which refers to statement 3 and 4. In total, the respondents’ perceived organizational dynamics experienced in terms of Benevolent Authoritative is “mostly experienced”.

Table 4. Organizational Dynamics Experienced in terms of Participative Strategy

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school...			
1. full confidence and trust are manifested in all school personnel.	4.39	0.57	ME
2. decisions are formed through group participation and consultation.	4.37	0.62	ME
3. teamwork, satisfaction and productivity are high	4.41	0.58	ME
4. open communication is applied and managers actively try to understand issues.	4.41	0.58	ME
1. full confidence and trust are manifested in all school personnel.	4.42	0.56	ME
Overall	4.40	0.59	ME

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Experienced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Experienced, 2.50-3.49 Experienced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Experienced, 1.00-1.49 Not Experienced

Table 4 shows that respondents rated “mostly experienced” all statement above. The overall mean of (4.40) and a standard deviation of 0.59 implies that respondent’s perception of participative work culture in terms of Participative Strategy is mostly experienced.

Table 5. Organizational Dynamics Experienced in terms of Consultative Strategy

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school...			
1. responsibility is often shared with team members.	4.44	0.56	ME
2. substantial trust in school personnel is evident.	4.35	0.58	ME
3. teams are more cooperative-communication and teamwork are visible.	4.43	0.56	ME
4. motivation is primarily done through reward system.	4.11	0.93	ME
5. employees discuss job-related issues.	4.32	0.63	ME
Overall	4.33	0.65	ME

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Experienced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Experienced, 2.50-3.49 Experienced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Experienced, 1.00-1.49 Not Experienced

Table 5 shows that respondents rated agree all indicative statement above. The overall mean of (4.33) and a standard deviation of 0.65 implies that respondent’s perception of participative work culture in terms of consultative strategy is mostly experienced.

Table 6. Respondents Perception of Participative Work Culture in terms of Affiliations

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school, teachers...			
1. express the interest-driven aspect of participatory culture.	4.22	0.57	MP
2. include member with a range of ability levels.	4.20	0.62	MP
3. participate in circulation networks outside the school.	4.11	0.66	MP
4. enable members to pursue new interest.	4.23	0.61	MP
5. encourage educators to participate in public platforms.	4.25	0.57	MP
Overall	4.20	0.61	MP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

As presented in Table 6, respondents rated mostly practiced the all statement above. The overall mean of (4.20) and a standard deviation of 0.61 implies that respondent's perception of participative work culture in terms of affiliations is mostly practiced. This is essential social activity of interacting with others who share interests. Committed teachers are affiliated with the school they work for and they invest their time and energy promoting the school.

Table 7. Respondents Perception of Participative Work Culture in terms of Expressions

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school, teachers...			
1. engage in cycles of conceiving, representing and sharing ideas.	4.36	0.53	MP
2. communicate like veteran members.	4.23	0.62	MP
3. build pupil's interest and authentic audiences.	4.37	0.57	MP
4. share work with interested audiences.	4.35	0.57	MP
5. form a bridge based upon the resilient structures of participatory cultures.	4.29	0.60	MP
Overall	4.32	0.58	MP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

Table 7 reveals that there are five indicative statement obtained the highest mean interpreted as "mostly practiced". In total, the respondents' perceived participative work culture in terms of expressions is "mostly practiced" (M=4.32, SD=0.58).

It implies that members become more familiar with the culture, they begin to communicate like veteran members, discuss the work of other participants, and finally to produce like full members. Schools can move toward the design principle of expressions by building student interests and authentic audiences into daily practices.

Table 8. Respondents Perception of Participative Work Culture in terms of Collaborative Problem Solving.

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school, school head...			
1. provides positive feedback.	4.47	0.55	MP
2. distributes knowledge across the community.	4.39	0.59	MP
3. organizes to coordinate collaborative inquiry.	4.42	0.55	MP
4. struggles with collaborative problem solving.	4.02	1.05	MP
5. communicates effectively during collaboration.	4.38	0.59	MP
Overall	4.34	0.67	MP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

Table 8 reveals that there are five statement obtained the highest mean interpreted as "mostly practiced". In total, the respondents' perceived participative work culture in terms of collaborative problem solving is "mostly practiced" (M=4.34, SD=0.67). Collaboration between school head and teachers produces a number of benefits with significant impacts on their professional lives, thus playing an important role in professional teacher development strategy. LAC sessions encourage critical reflection amongst teachers which increases the understanding and knowledge of the curriculum and classroom practices.

Table 9. Respondents perception of Participative Work Culture in terms of Circulations

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school...			
1. pupils participate circulation networks outside the school.	4.17	0.68	MP
2. members pursue new interest.	4.27	0.64	MP
3. educators participate in public platforms.	4.24	0.58	MP
4. educators bring solutions to address the problems.	4.33	0.57	MP
1. cultivate extended and virtual professional learning.	4.32	0.61	MP
Overall	4.26	0.62	MP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

Table 9 reveals that there are five statement obtained the highest mean interpreted as "mostly practiced". In total, the respondents' perceived participative work culture in terms of circulations is "mostly practiced" (M=4.26, SD=0.62).

Educators bring solution to address the problems interpreted "mostly practiced" it implies that positive and respectful problem-solving help the teacher work towards a solution. Be a positive role model for learners by being positive, thinking about solutions.

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

The happy or satisfied feeling of the teachers towards organization affects the overall process in carrying their job, thus, contributes to the school success.

Table 10. Teachers Effectiveness in terms of Professional growth.

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school, school heads...			
1. supports teachers professional growth .	4.62	0.49	HE
2. encourages teachers to participate in all activities that may contribute professional growth.	4.58	0.53	HE
3. acquired new professional outlook and new skills.	4.57	0.53	HE
4. supports to developments in education through seminars and trainings.	4.54	0.59	HE
5. motivates teachers to use variety of teaching methods, strategies, and resources to differentiate instruction and promote learning for all pupils.	4.58	0.54	HE
Overall	4.58	0.54	HE

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Effective, 3.50-4.49 Effective, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Effective, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Effective, 1.00-1.49 Not Effective

Table 10 reveals that there are five indicative statement obtained the highest mean interpreted as “highly effective”. In total, the respondents’ perception about the teacher’s professional growth is “highly effective” (M=4.58, SD=0.54). The results revealed that in Tiaong 1 District school heads/leaders supports teacher’s professional development .Professional Training may be used in reference to a wide variety of specialized training, formal education, or advanced professional learning intended to help administrators, teachers, and other educators improve their professional knowledge, competence, skill, and effectiveness.

Table 11. Teachers Effectiveness in terms of Teaching Style

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school, the teachers...			
1. selected, prepared, and utilized available technology and other instructional materials appropriate to the learners.	4.52	0.57	HE
2. used technology to explore and reach understanding in different concepts.	4.53	0.56	HE
3. delivered accurate and updated content knowledge using appropriate methodologies, approaches, and strategies.	4.56	0.59	HE
4. made good use of allotted instructional time.	4.49	0.60	E
5. embraced changes in school organization.	4.48	0.57	E
Overall	4.52	0.58	HE

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Effective, 3.50-4.49 Effective, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Effective, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Effective, 1.00-1.49 Not Effective

Table 11 shows statement that involves teacher’s performance in terms of teaching style got the highest mean of 4.53 with a verbal interpretation of “highly effective” and a standard deviation of 0.56. This reveals that in every corner of the school, teachers delivered accurate and content knowledge using appropriate methodologies, approaches, and strategies in terms of teaching style

Table 12. Learning Outcomes in terms of Intellectual Skills.

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school, teachers ...			
1. made sure that the learning skills of pupils are enhanced.	4.57	0.52	HP
2. communicated and helped pupils to recall the component of the lesson.	4.57	0.50	HP
3. provided technical assistance to pupils.	4.53	0.55	HP
4. teaches or recalls relevant rules and information.	4.52	0.54	HP
5. engaged pupils in discovery learning to find a solution.	4.54	0.55	HP
Overall	4.55	0.54	HP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

As presented in Table 12, respondents rated Highly practiced all the statement above. The overall mean of (4.55) and a standard deviation of 0.54 implies that learning outcomes in Cognitive strategy is Highly practiced.

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

In total, the respondents' perceived that the level of learning outcomes in terms of intellectual skills is "outstanding". It implies that teacher do everything to teach the learners. They also conduct remediation to those slow learners. In fact, the effort of the teacher is one of the basis of good performance in the field.

Table 13. Learning Outcomes in terms of Cognitive Strategy.

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school, teachers...			
1. explain learning goals, instructional procedures, and content, clearly and accurately to pupils.	4.51	0.53	HP
2. help pupils find new solutions to problem.	4.52	0.54	HP
3. help pupils explore and understand how ideas are connected.	4.51	0.53	HP
4. demonstrate positive attitude to solve problems in a classroom situation.	4.52	0.53	HP
5. engage and sustains learner's interest in the subject matter by making content meaningful and relevant.	4.53	0.53	HP
Overall	4.52	0.54	HP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

As presented in Table 13, respondents rated Highly practiced all the statement above. The overall mean of (4.52) and a standard deviation of 0.54 it implies that learning outcomes in Cognitive strategy is Highly practiced.

Statement 5 interpreted as Highly practiced implies that interest is a powerful motivational process that energizes learning, guides academic and it is essential to academic success. Interest is both a psychological state of attention and affect toward a particular object or topic. Teacher's knowledge includes all the required cognitive strategy for creating effective teaching and learning environments and assess their implications for the instructional process and to derive evidence-based suggestions for educational policy.

Table 14. Learning Outcomes in terms of Verbal Information.

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school, teachers...			
1. teach pupils different mnemonic techniques.	4.40	0.61	MP
2. provide distinct cues to assist memory.	4.39	0.59	MP
3. guided pupils relate new information to what already exist in memory to make learning meaningful.	4.48	0.54	MP
4. help pupils with learning difficulties.	4.58	0.51	HP
5. organize, elaborate and rehearse to assist in learning declarative knowledge.	4.47	0.55	MP
Overall	4.47	0.56	MP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

Table 14 reveals that there are four statement obtained the highest mean interpreted as "mostly practiced" and interpreted as "Highly practiced" which refers to statement r 4. In total, the respondents' perceived learning outcomes in terms of verbal information is "mostly practiced" (M=4.47, SD=0.56).

Pupils need to know the various types of sources indicator 4 interpreted Highly Practiced help pupils with learning difficulties. Teachers can make learning participative, encourage peer learning and encourage learners to ask for help-show that this is acceptable and is not a sign of failure.

Table 15. Learning Outcomes in terms of Motor Skills.

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
In school, teachers...			
1. develop learners skills by providing different activities.	4.58	0.51	HP
2. assist learner move in right direction.	4.54	0.53	HP
3. assesses in complex performances such as dancing and writing.	4.49	0.58	MP
4. execute sample movements such as playing with learners.	4.49	0.57	MP
5. involve learners in motor skills like learning to write and playing musical instrument.	4.46	0.61	MP
Overall	4.51	0.56	HP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

As presented in Table 15, respondents rated Highly practiced in overall. The overall mean of (4.51) and a standard deviation of 0.56 implies that learning outcomes in terms of motor skill is Highly practiced. It signifies that the respondents are very much familiar on the different techniques in teaching in terms of motor skills teachers helps the learners by providing different activities that will develop their fine and gross motor skills. They are able to access a wider source of learning activities, and social experiences

Table 16. Learning Outcomes in terms of Attitude.

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The school manifests....			
1. willingness to share the responsibility involved.	4.52	0.55	HP
2. open-mindedness for all the changes being encountered	4.52	0.55	HP
3. teachers who exert best effort to help the school to achieve its goal.	4.52	0.55	HP
4. honesty in performing all activities.	4.56	0.53	HP
5. adherence to the ethics of being a teacher.	4.58	0.51	HP
Overall	4.54	0.54	HP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

The respondents' perceived that the level of learning outcome in terms of attitude is "Highly practiced" (M=4.54, SD=0.54). Teachers are always advocates rights and needs appropriately to ensure that there are no discriminations. Teachers also express interest and understanding because we are handling different attitudes of the learners.

Table 17. School Impact in terms of Enrolment.

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The school...			
1. developed best strategy for pupils recruitment.	4.45	0.58	MP
2. prepared and implements a well-defined enrolment process.	4.47	0.55	MP
3. emphasized warmth, consideration, and concern to prospective pupils and parents.	4.48	0.52	MP
4. satisfied with the quality of academic program.	4.46	0.58	MP
5. developed more homogeneous social circle for pupils.	4.40	0.65	MP
Overall	4.45	0.58	MP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

The respondents' perceived that the level of School impact in terms of enrolment is "mostly practiced" (M=4.45, SD=0.58). Schools are considered places that provide an appropriate learning environment for learners. The school emphasizes warmth, consideration, and concern to prospective pupils and parents. Sharing the story of school plays a hugely important part in any recruitment strategy

Table 18. School Impact in terms of Accreditation.

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The school....			
1. sets quality standards for educations programs.	4.46	0.57	MP
2. boosts public trust and confidence.	4.46	0.56	MP
3. ensures accountability of personnel.	4.44	0.56	MP
4. enhances teaching standards and learning outcomes through SBM validation.	4.41	0.59	MP
5. performs quality control to ensure pupils gain the content knowledge and academic skills.	4.42	0.54	MP
Overall	4.44	0.57	MP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

As presented in Table 18, respondents are Mostly Practiced all the indicative statement above. The overall mean of (4.44) and a standard deviation of 0.57 implies that School impact in terms of accreditation is Mostly practiced. School improvement is one of the leading educational programs initiated and adopted by many countries to provide quality education (Plan International, 2014). Furthermore, when there is a vibrant classroom, when teachers and school administrators are educated and informed, and when families and communities act an active role in supporting schools, children can learn to their full potential. (Stephen and Mundy 2014).

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

Table 19. School Impact in terms of Awards.

Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
The school...			
1. has an existing awards system recognizes work that show significant innovation.	4.38	0.64	MP
2. motivates teachers and pupils to acquire new skills.	4.49	0.57	MP
3. recognizes pupils for their efforts and hard work.	4.54	0.52	HP
4. enhances self-esteem of pupils.	4.53	0.57	HP
5. motivates pupils to work harder.	4.54	0.54	HP
Overall	4.50	0.57	HP

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Practiced, 3.50-4.49 Mostly Practiced, 2.50-3.49 Practiced, 1.50-2.49 Slightly Practiced, 1.00-1.49 Not Practiced

Table 19 reveals that there are three statement obtained the highest mean interpreted as “Highly practiced” and interpreted as “Mostly practiced” which refers to statement 1 and 2. In total, the respondents’ perceived organizational dynamics experienced in terms of Benevolent Authoritative is “Mostly practiced” (M=4.50, SD=1.50).

Tiaong 1 District recognized the best implementing schools and partners in the implementation of Brigada Eskwela Program. This award is great impact in school for an existing awards system and recognizes efforts and hard work that show significant innovation. Also different schools from Tiaong 1 District were recognized in different competition in terms of academic, sports and other extra-curricular activities.

Table 20. Correlation of Organizational Dynamics on School Environment Effectiveness

Organization al dynamics	Teachers’ Performance		Learning Outcome				School Impact			
	Profess ional Growth	Teachi ng Style	Intellect ual skills	Cognitive strategy	Verbal informa tion	Motor skills	Attitude	Enrolment	Accredi tation	Awards
	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value
exploitative	.156*	.202**	.221**	.224**	.354**	.316**	.292**	.287**	.262**	.190*
authoritative										
benevolent	.169*	.228**	.225**	.182*	.360**	.304**	.281**	.316**	.277**	.234**
authoritative										
participative	.632**	.481**	.574**	.602**	.564**	.564**	.631**	.560**	.541**	.526**
consultative	.561**	.480**	.537**	.499**	.543**	.553**	.604**	.607**	.544**	.541**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

As shown in Table 1, the correlation between significant organizational dynamics when it comes to school environment effectiveness was sustained. It implies that the test of significant relationship of organizational dynamics and school environment shows positive significant relationship. Successful leaders have to care about school culture, pay attention to the pressures of change and holistically evaluate their organizations' environment. Specifically, the wide-angle view related to the school culture offers leaders a broader framework for a deeper understanding of school climate and complex relationships within the school organization. IPCRF is an assessment tool to rate teachers for their annual accomplishments. It is a shared undertaking between the school head and the teachers that allows an open discussion of course expectations, key results areas, objectives and how these align to overall departmental goals. LAC session program of the Department of Education aims to create professional learning communities that will help teachers to have a wider scope of teaching content and methodologies.

In Tiaong, classroom observation done by school principal in order to provide technical assistance and instructional pedagogy in teaching mandated by DepEd Memorandum no. 008,s. 2023 known as the Multi-Year guidelines on the Result-Based Performance Manangement System-Philippine professional satandards for teachers. Each teacher was given technical assistance by the principal after classroom observation.

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

Table 21. Correlation of Participative Work Culture on School Environment Effectiveness

	Teachers' Performance		Learning Outcome				School Impact				
	practice of participative work culture	Professional Growth	Teaching Style	Intellectual skills	Cognitive strategy	Verbal information	Motor skills	Attitude	Enrollment	Accreditation	Awards
	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value	R-value
affiliations	.501**	.545**	.630**	.521**	.660*	.651**	.555**	.575**	.606**	.535**	
expressions	.524**	.569**	.633**	.587**	.644**	.691**	.625**	.624**	.630**	.574**	
collaborative problem solving	.585**	.506**	.548**	.496**	.605**	.615**	.584**	.559**	.554**	.511**	
circulations	.563**	.514**	.631**	.587**	.674**	.657**	.560**	.610**	.582**	.567**	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As shown in Table 2, the correlation between Participative work culture and school environment effectiveness. It can be gleaned from the table, that the variables under teachers' performance which include affiliations, expressions, collaborative problem solving and circulations was found significantly related to learning outcome and school impact.

The result may imply that learning outcome are an essential part of any unit outline. A learning outcome is a clear statement of what a learner is expected to be able to do, know about and/or value at the completion of a unit of study, and how well they should be expected to achieve those outcomes. It states both the substance of learning and how its attainment is to be demonstrated. An effective set of learning outcomes statements informs and guides teachers and pupils. For teaching staff, it informs the content of teaching, the teaching strategies you will use, the sorts of learning activities/tasks you set for your students, appropriate assessment tasks and evaluation. Improved Communication and Collaboration in a participative work culture fosters open communication channels and encourages collaboration among stakeholders, including teachers, administrators, students, and parents. When individuals have the opportunity to actively participate in decision-making processes, share their ideas, and engage in meaningful dialogue, it leads to better understanding, alignment, and cooperation within the school environment (Kanter, 2018).

Enhanced communication and collaboration positively impact the overall effectiveness of the school environment. Likewise, Increased Ownership and Engagement in Participative work cultures empower individuals and give them a sense of ownership in their work and the school environment. When teachers and other staff members feel valued and involved in decision-making, they become more engaged and committed to their roles (Barkhuizen et al., 2017). This increased ownership and engagement translate into improved teaching practices, better student support, and a positive learning atmosphere, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of the school environment. Moreover, Enhanced Problem-solving and Innovation in a participative work culture encourages diverse perspectives and ideas, promoting problem-solving and innovation within the school environment. When individuals are given the opportunity to contribute their insights and experiences, they bring fresh ideas to address challenges and find creative solutions (Davis et al., 2019).

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the of the study findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. There is a significant relationship between the experienced organizational dynamics and school environment effectiveness. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated in study is not supported.
2. Participative work culture is significantly related to school environment effectiveness in terms of teachers' performance, learning outcome and school impact. Therefore, the null hypothesis stated in study is not supported.

6. RECOMMENDATION

In the light of the conclusions of the study the following recommendations are set forth:

1. The study recommends that the school heads and principal in every school may develop training about effective communication skills. It's important to develop listening skills and encourage members of an organization to share their ideas. This management structure, group success is just as valuable as individual success. Administrators may give due and proper recognition of outstanding performance to deserving teachers. It will inspire them and others to develop and strengthen their personal and professional qualities.

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

2. School administrators may develop program or series of activities to enhance the competence of the teachers. Teachers should have the initiative to upgrade their teaching skills and competencies by attending seminars and trainings as frequently as possible to keep modern trends and issues teaching and teaching strategies.

3. For the researchers, a similar study of this kind may be conducted to support or deny the findings of this investigation. This could clarify and strengthen the conclusion of this study. The researcher also trusts that results may stimulate further research into other equally important aspects that relate to organizational dynamics and participative work culture in a school environment. This study may hopefully contribute to the general understanding the effect of organizational dynamics and participative work culture in appraising school environment effectiveness.

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REFERENCES

- 1) Adriano (2011) Collaboration: A Framework for School Improvement <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ984546.pdf>.
- 2) Aliazas, V.M . & Elisa N. (2021) Work Culture and Learning Organization Practices in Promoting Work Productivity among Public Elementary School Teachers. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*, 2 (3), 39-60.
- 3) Almendrada, Q. (2014) Attitudes of school elementary principals and Teachers in implementation of the school based management in the District of Alaminos, Laguna State Polytechnic University.
- 4) Antonakis, J., House, R. J., & Simonton, D. K. (2017). Can super smart leaders suffer from too much of a good thing? The curvilinear effect of intelligence on perceived leadership behavior. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 102(7), 1003–1021. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0000221> *Appraisal: Ratings as a Function of the Degree of Performance Responsibility*.
- 5) Associate Professor, Department of Sociology, SBS PG College, Ummedpur, Etah. *Journal of Business Management & Quality Assurance* Vol 1 No 1. (2017)
- 6) Atasoy (2020) The Relationship Between School Principals' Leadership Styles, School Culture and Organizational Change *International Journal of Progressive Education*, Volume 16 Number 5, 2020 © 2020 INASED
- 7) Bantugan, Rosario C. (2009) Institutionalizing School Learning Action Cell as a Key for Teacher's Continuous Learning and Development.
- 8) Barkhuizen, G., Van Vuuren, L. J., & Schutte, C. S. L. (2017). Teachers' perceptions of their participation in decision-making in schools. *Perspectives in Education*, 35(1), 137-152. 2.
- 9) Barnett, Kerry and Lee, Chua Leadership and Individual Principal-Teacher Relationships in Schools, August 2004
- 10) (Barkhuizen et al., 2017). Narrative Approaches to Exploring Language, Identity and Power in Language Teacher Education DOI:[10.1177/0033688216631222](https://doi.org/10.1177/0033688216631222)
- 11) Beauchamp (2021) A Formal Administrator Mentoring Program: Perceived Learning Benefits and Insights into Leadership Well-being Volume 13 Issue 1 Article 3
- 12) Bhandari, (2021) Correlational Research <https://opentextbc.ca/researchmethods/chapter/correlational-research/>
- 13) Bruns, B., Filmer, D. and Patrinos, H. A. (2017) Making schools work: New evidence on accountability reforms. [Online URL: <http://siteresources.worldbank.org/EDUCATION/Resources/278200-1298568319076/makingschoolswork.pdf>] accessed on March 7, 2018.
- 14) Ciriaka, D. (2003). Nurturing innovation: how much does collaborative management help? *The International Journal of Educational Management*, 13 (3), 114-125.
- 15) Corpuz, B. (2007). Principle of Teaching. Quezon City: Lorimar Publishing
- 16) Corpuz, B. (2007). Principle of Teaching. Quezon City: Lorimar Publishing
- 17) Cranston (2016) Organizational Success: 10 Proven Ways to Transform Your Business Jul 14, 2022 | [Performance Management, Professional Development](#)
- 18) Cranston, J. W. (2011). Market-oriented sustainability: moderating impact of stakeholder involvement.). *Decision support system for stakeholder involvement*
- 19) Cranston, J. W. (2016). Market-oriented sustainability: moderating impact of stakeholder involvement. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*.
- 20) Davis, T., Darmanin, M., & Zammit, S. (2019). Participatory leadership and school effectiveness: A review of empirical research. *School Leadership & Management*, 39(4), 351-372.
- 21) Dembo, M. H. & Gibson, S. (1985): Teachers Sense of Efficacy: An Important
- 22) Desimone (2013) Improving Impact Studies of Teachers' Professional Development: Toward Better Conceptualizations and Measures DOI:[10.3102/0013189X08331140](https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X08331140) *Educational Researcher* 38(3):181-199

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

- 23) Dimaisip, J.S (2022) Principle Centered Management and Multitasking Strategies in Fostering Organizational Effectiveness DOI: [10.47119/IJRP1001071820223767](https://doi.org/10.47119/IJRP1001071820223767)
- 24) Dimmock, J. D. (2000). Corporate governance and management practices: stakeholder involvement, quality and sustainability tools adoption. *Journal of Management & Governance*, 17(4), 907-937.
- 25) Dumas, Rosalinda M. (2010) "Leadership Style and Management Competencies of School Heads, Impact on Teacher's Job Performance"
- 26) Edge, S. (2000). What have we learned about stakeholder involvement in program evaluation? *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 34(4), 224-230
- 27) Elliott, Kerry (2015) "Teacher Performance Appraisal: More about Performance or Development?," *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*: Vol. 40: Iss. 9 Article 6. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2015v40n9.6>
- 28) Espiritu (2012) Can Co-curricular Activities Enhance the Learning Effectiveness of Students? :An Application to the Sub-degree Students in Hong Kong 2011, Volume 23, Number 3, 329-341 Factor in School Improvement. *The Elementary School Journal*, 86, 173-184.
- 29) Freeman, R.E. (1984), *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*, Pitman: Boston, MA.
- 30) General Teaching Council for England (2005). What do studies of continuing professional development (CPD) tell us about the factors which help professional growth of teachers and pupil learning? London: GTCE.
- 31) Getange, K. N. (2016) Motivational Strategies and teachers' productivity: lessons of experience from public secondary school in Kisumu Country, Kenya. *Journal of research and methods in education*, 6(4), 33-38
- 32) Great Schools Partnership, (2014) | 482 Congress Street, Suite 500 | Portland, ME 04101 | 207.773.0505 | greatschoolspartnership.org
- 33) Gupta, S. (2017). *Higher Education Management, Policies and Strategies*.
- 34) Hassan, M. M., Mutambara, E., & Binta, A. I. (2018). Leadership styles and school effectiveness: Empirical evidence from secondary schools in the Gambia. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 46(4), 546-562.
- 35) Henderson, A. & Mapp, K. (2002). *A New Wave of Evidence: The Impact of School, Family and Community Connections on Student Achievement*. Austin, TX: Southwest Educational Development Corporation (SEDL)
- 36) Hopkins, D. (2005) *in an Organization as a Result of Performance Appraisal*. Blekinge Institute of Technology. 2012 *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*, Volume 2, Issue 3, pp. 39 - 60.
- 37) Janse (2019) Likert's Management Systems <https://www.businessballs.com/organisational-culture/likerts-management-systems/>
- 38) Janse (2019) Rensis Likert's Management Systems are powerful theories of leadership which highlight various organisational dynamics and characteristics. Jenkins (2012)
- 39) Jenkins on Participatory Culture <https://newlearningonline.com/literacies/chapter-7/jenkins-on-participatory-culture>
- 40) Jing (2017) Participative Leadership: What It Can Do for Organizations <https://www.pon.harvard.edu/daily/leadership-skills-daily/participative-leadership-what-it-can-do-for-organization>.
- 41) Kanter, R. M. (2018). *The power of a positive no: How to say no and still get to yes*. Bantam.
- 42) Licaycay (2015) Perception of teaching as a profession and UB teacher trainees' attitude towards training programme and teaching Vol. 10(21), pp. 2797-2805, 10 November, 2015 DOI: 10.5897/ERR2015.2441
- 43) McCombes, (2019) Psychologists Use Descriptive, Correlational, and Experimental Research Designs to Understand Behaviour <https://opentextbc.ca/introductiontopsychology/chapter/2-2-psychologists-use-descriptive-correlational-and-experimental-research-designs-to-understand-behavior>
- 44) Mohan (2021) *Organizational effectiveness: The X factor for company success*
- 45) Morgan P, J. (2012) Using Gagne's Learning Outcome The educational psychologist, Robert Gagne set forth five categories of learning outcomes: <https://pamelajmorgan.org/2011/03/17/using-gagnes-learning-outcomes/>
- 46) Mukolwe, Josep, O, dkk, (2017). Implementation of Total Quality Management In Natasa, P. (2011). *The meaning of teacher competence in contexts of change* Print. Zuidam Uithor Drukkerjen-978-90-393-5695
- 47) Olasunkanmi, A & Ademola. (2012) *Attitude of Employees to Work Performance*
- 48) Pham (2018) Impacts of higher education quality accreditation: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13538322.2018.1491787> Primary Schools as A Panacea for Low Academic Achievement, *European Journal of Research in Social Sciences*
- 49) Procedia (2015) 5th World Conference on Learning, Teaching and Educational Leadership, WCLTA 2014 Education, Teaching and School as A Social Organization Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences 186 (2015) 381 – 387
- 50) Rutter, M & Maughan, B. (2002): School Effectiveness Findings. *Journal of Scheren* (2016) *Organizational Success: Factors & Definition* <https://study.com/academy/lesson/organizational-success-factors-definition-quiz.html> School Psychology, 451-472

Organizational Dynamics and Participative Work Culture in Appraising School Environment Effectiveness

- 50) Stroet (2013) Effects of need supportive teaching on early adolescents' motivation and engagement: A review of the literature *Educational Research Review* 9:65–87 DOI:[10.1016/j.edurev.2012.11.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2012.11.003)
- 51) Suharsaputra & Simanjuntak, (2013) The Influence of The Transformational Leadership and Work Motivation on Teachers Performance
- 52) Sutton C.L. & Dobbins G.H. (2011). *Person and System Effects Performance*
- 53) Tobergte, D. R. and Curtis, S. (2013) Do you see what I see? The impact of school accountability on parent, teacher, and student perceptions of the school environment. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*
- 54) Zhong (2016) Effectiveness of Performance Management System for Employee Performance Through Engagement <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2158244020969383>
- 55) Zylfijaj (2014) Parrticipative Leadership Theory And Decision-Making Style <https://www.simplypsychology.org/participative-leadership>.